

PHOTONICS METROLOGY IN THE NANOSCALE

Stephan Reichelt¹, Karsten Frenner¹, Christian Schober¹ and Christof Pruss¹

¹Institute of Applied Optics, University of Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 9, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany

ABSTRACT

Optical metrology at the nanoscale level is a sophisticated task, where often model-based approaches are utilized. We discuss scatterometry in an advanced implementation as well as some of the capabilities of our Nanopositioning and Nanomeasuring Machine (NPMM-200).

KEYWORDS: Nanometrology, Model-based optical scatterometry, White-light interferometry, Mueller polarimetry, Large-volume Nanopositioning and Nanomeasuring Machine (NPMM-200)

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is one of today's key technologies, enabling a wide range of applications. The most prominent example of the ongoing trend towards further miniaturization is undoubtedly optical lithography, which is used to manufacture highly integrated circuits and leading edge microchips. The advances in nanotechnology are closely related to the progress in nanometrology. As with any technology, reliable processes and mass production are only possible if structures and objects can be measured with a high degree of reliability and if traceability is provided. In general, nanometrology involves all the structural, chemical, electronic or optical properties of a nanostructure. A structure or object is said to be nanoscale if it is between one and 100 nanometers in at least one dimension.

In the first part of this contribution we present optical methods that are related to the structural examination of dimensional features (critical dimension, period, height, side wall angles, line edge roughness, etc.) of complex periodic sub-lambda structures used in semiconductor industry. In particular, we discuss model-based optical scatterometry, which is the standard metrology technique in semiconductor manufacturing.

In the second part we present the basic principle and some of the capabilities of the Nanopositioning and Nanomeasuring Machine (NPMM-200), developed at TU Ilmenau. One of the two existing machines is installed at ITO to explore new concepts for 3D nanometrology over a large measurement volume of 200 mm × 200 mm × 25 mm.

OPTICAL NANOMETROLOGY – MEASUREMENT AT NANOSCALE LEVEL

The current accuracy requirements of optical metrology in semiconductor industry are two orders of magnitude beyond the diffraction limit of visible-wavelength microscopy. In practice, optical nanometrology is an indirect measurement technique because conventional microscopic imaging at actinic wavelengths is not available due to complexity and cost.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of a white-light Mueller matrix Fourier scatterometry sensor [1].

The need to resolve structural details in the traditional sense is increasingly replaced by a highly accurate model-based object reconstruction. Solving the inverse problem, i.e. retrieving one-dimensional features of periodic nanostructures from measured light field signatures, requires a detailed understanding of the interaction of light with the structure under study. This is a challenging task, because not only the feature size becomes smaller and smaller, but also their complexity is increasing with the 3D integration of semiconductor devices.

To account for the large parameter space that comes along with the increasing design complexity, Fourier scatterometry has been combined with the classical techniques of white-light interferometry and Mueller polarimetry. The system comprises a combination of a Fourier-plane microscope, a Fourier-transform spectrometer based on a Linnik interferometer, and a polarimeter. The implementation and measurement results are presented.

NANOPOSITIONING AND NANOMEASURING MACHINE NPMM-200

The Nanopositioning and Nanomeasuring Machine (NPMM-200) was built to address the increasing demand for high-precision metrology over large areas. It is capable to address a measurement volume of 200 mm in square and 25 mm in depth with sub nanometer resolution (cf. Table 1). The metrological frame is made of ZERODUR® to which the probe system and the interferometers are attached. The kinematic concept is realized in a sample scanning mode: the probing point is fixed in space, whereas the sample under test is positioned in 3D space. The sample is mounted on a three-sided mirrored stage whose position is measured by 6 interferometers in all 6 degrees of freedom relative to the metrological frame. Abbe errors are minimized by aligning the axes of the interferometers so that they intersect at one point in space that ideally coincides with the probing point. The entire system is closed loop controlled.

Different types of sensors can be attached to the metrological frame. As examples, we present measurements using an auto focus probe on a step height normal and shape measurements of freeform surfaces. In addition we implemented a custom-built coherence scanning interferometer probe for measuring aspheres and freeform surfaces with high lateral resolution.

Figure 2: (a) Metrological frame with the mirror corner and interferometers, (b) Opened vacuum chamber of the NPMM-200 [2].

Table 1: Some specifications of the NPMM-200.

Parameter	Value
Positioning volume	200 mm × 200 mm × 25 mm
Positioning reproducibility	≤ 4 nm
Resolution	≤ 0.08 nm
Positioning speed	30 mm/s
3D-uncertainty	≤ 30 nm (2σ)
Sample weight	≤ 2.5 kg
Sample size	≤ 310 mm × 310 mm × 90 mm
Sensors	anything < 15 kg (optical, AFM, ...)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the contributions of M. L. Gödecke, V. Ferreras Paz, and others that have worked at ITO under the supervision of W. Osten. This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. L. Gödecke, et al., „Model-based characterisation of complex periodic nanostructures by white-light Mueller-matrix Fourier scatterometry” *Light: Advanced Manufacturing* 2, 18(2021).
- [2] C. Schober, et al., "The NPMM-200: large area high resolution for freeform surface measurement," Proc. SPIE 11478, 1147807 (2020).

CONTACT

* Stephan Reichelt; phone: ++49 (711) 685-66075; reichelt@ito.uni-stuttgart.de